

DETECTING AND CLASSIFYING BRAIN TUMORS FROM MULTI-CHANNEL MRIS USING DEEP LEARNING AND TRANSFER LEARNING TECHNIQUES

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DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10228221>

MAZEDAN COMPUTER
ENGINEERING TRANSACTIONS

e-ISSN: 2583-0414

Article id: MCET0401003

Vol.-4, Issue-1

Received: 19 Feb 2023

Revised: 27 Mar 2023

Accepted: 2 Apr 2023

Citation: Khan, F., & Kumar, M. (2023). Detecting and Classifying Brain Tumors from Multi-Channel MRIs using Deep Learning and Transfer Learning Techniques. *Mazedan Computer Engineering Transactions*, 4(1), 24-31.

Abstract

Approximately 80% of malignant primary brain tumors in adults are Glioblastoma Multiforme, which is usually classified as either High Grade Glioma (HGG) or Low-Grade Glioma (LGG). Compared to HGG tumors, LGG tumors develop more slowly and are less aggressive, and they frequently respond well to treatment. The difficulties in performing tumor biopsies on patients with brain tumors have made noninvasive imaging methods, such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), indispensable for the diagnosis of these disorders. Thus, it is now essential to build automated systems that can identify and forecast tumor grades using MRI data.

This paper investigates the use of multisequence MR images to classify brain cancers using Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (ConvNets). We propose and train a novel ConvNet on MRI multi-planar volumetric slices from scratch. Furthermore, two ConvNet models that were previously trained on the ImageNet dataset—VGGNet and ResNet101—are fine-tuned in order to examine the applicability of transfer learning. Specifically, the final few layers of both models are adjusted. ConvNet performance is assessed by the use of a Leave-one-patient-out (LOPO) testing scheme.

The findings show that training on the multi-planar volumetric dataset improves accuracy for ConvNet, which reaches a testing accuracy of 97% without requiring extra work in feature extraction and selection, which is typically necessary for conventional models. When compared to the most advanced techniques, which for this task need manual feature engineering, ConvNets' grading performance is improved by up to 12%.

Keywords— Glioblastoma Multiforme, MRI, Deep Convolutional Neural Networks, Transfer learning, Brain cancer

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) has emerged as the established non-invasive approach for identifying brain malignancies, owing mostly to its improved soft tissue contrast [1][2]. Gliomas, which originate in the central nervous system from glial cells, account for 80% of all malignant brain tumors. The World Health Organization (WHO) divides gliomas into two categories based on their aggressiveness and infiltrative nature: low-grade and intermediate-grade gliomas (WHO grades II and III), and high-grade gliomas (HGG) or glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) (WHO grade IV) [3]. While most LGG tumors develop at a slower rate than HGG and react well to treatment, a fraction of LGG tumors may proceed to GBM if not detected early and untreated. In all circumstances, precise treatment planning combining surgery, radiation, and chemotherapy, either alone or in combination, is critical. Recognizing that early and precise diagnosis of tumor grade can have a major impact on prognosis [4].

Histological grading, which is performed using a stereotactic biopsy technique, is the gold standard for establishing the grade of a brain tumor. A neurosurgeon

uses specialized equipment to drill a small hole into the skull at the precise site of the tumor, as indicated by MRI. However, there are various risks associated with the biopsy test, such as bleeding from the tumor and brain caused by the biopsy needle, which can result in serious problems such as headaches, strokes, coma, and even death. Other concerns include the possibility of infection or convulsions. The fundamental difficulty with stereotactic biopsy is its lack of precision. When it misguides tumor histological grading, it can result in a major diagnostic error, leading to inappropriate disease management [5].

Multi-sequence MRI adds greatly to the non-invasive detection, diagnosis, and therapy of brain tumors in this context. Recent research suggests that automatic computerized disease identification and diagnosis based on medical image analysis could be a feasible option. Radiomics, or the noninvasive decoding of tumor phenotype, is a booming subject in current research [6][7][8]. This field entails extracting multiple

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quantitative imaging elements from medical images that are not visible to the naked eye. The human or automated delineation of the 2D region of interest (ROI) or 3D volume of interest (VOI) [9][10][11][12] is a critical stage in the technique for focusing attention on malignant development. Following that, appropriate sets of hand-crafted quantitative imaging features are retrieved from the ROI or VOI, and these features are then subjected to machine learning analysis for decision-making. Feature selection becomes critical in this process because it allows for the removal of duplicate and/or less significant subsets of characteristics, which contributes to gains in both performance speed and accuracy. This is especially true for high-dimensional radiomic characteristics derived from image data.

Researchers have investigated quantitative imaging features extracted from MR images for the evaluation of brain malignancies in the literature [8][13]. The authors of Reference [14] presented an adaptive neuro-fuzzy classifier based on linguistic hedges (ANFC-LH) to predict brain tumor grade using 56 3D quantitative MRI data collected from segmented tumor volumes. Another study investigated MR imaging variables to find those capable of discriminating between grades of soft-tissue sarcoma (STS) [15]. On images produced from each MR sequence, the investigated features included signal intensity, heterogeneity, margin, descriptive statistics, and perilesional properties. A study looked into brain tumor classification and grading based on 2D quantitative imaging parameters such texture and form, as well as gray-level co-occurrence, run-length, and morphological aspects [16].

While these methods are useful for illness categorization, their reliance on hand-crafted features raises difficulties. This reliance requires extensive domain expertise, adds human bias, and is intrinsically problem-specific. Manual feature design often necessitates a thorough grasp of the particular characteristics of normal and diseased tissues and may fall short of adequately capturing key representative aspects. This constraint may impair the classifier's performance.

Furthermore, due to the discriminative character of the approaches, where hand-crafted features are typically fitted to fixed training sets, the generalization capabilities of such classifiers may be impaired. Furthermore, manual or semi-automatic region of interest (ROI) or volume of interest (VOI) localization and segmentation are required for extracting quantitative imaging data [9][10].

Convolutional Neural Networks (ConvNets) are a cutting-edge framework for image detection and classification [17][18][19]. ConvNets' architecture is intended to loosely mimic the fundamental workings of the mammalian visual cortex system. According to research, the visual cortex has numerous layers of abstractions, each of which seeks certain patterns in the input vision. A ConvNet, in a similar vein, is built by stacking numerous layers, allowing it to learn various abstractions from the input data. These networks learn mid- and high-level representations or abstractions from the input training data using convolution filters that are updated during the training process. ConvNets learn hierarchically complicated underlying representative features directly

from raw input data, such as photographs, removing the need for specialized hand-crafted image features. Furthermore, ConvNets do not require prior domain expertise and may automatically learn and execute any task by analyzing training data.

However, training a ConvNet from scratch is often difficult, owing to the need for large training data as well as significant knowledge in designing an optimal model architecture to achieve good convergence. Data scarcity is a major difficulty in medical applications, and gaining expert annotations can be costly. Deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) training requires significant computational and memory resources, making the process time-consuming. Iterative changes to architecture and/or learning parameters, while avoiding overfitting, make deep learning from start laborious, time-consuming, and exhausting. Transfer learning emerges as a possible alternative in circumstances with insufficient data. This method entails fine-tuning an already-trained ConvNet on a large dataset of tagged images from a separate category [20]. This method can be used to hasten convergence and reduce computing complexity during training [21][22].

This research examines ConvNets, both with and without transfer learning, for non-invasive detection and grade prediction of brain cancers using multi-sequence MRI. We investigate the performance and complexity of ConvNets in light of the inherent heterogeneity of tumors based on cancer subtypes and their amalgamation of structural and patch-level variability. We undertake experiments with three types of datasets obtained from the original MRI dataset to understand the impact of input data format on ConvNets: i) Patch-based, ii) Slice-based, and iii) Volume-based. In each case, a ConvNet model is built and trained from the ground up. In addition, we assess the efficacy of two well-known convolutional neural network architectures, VGGNet [23] and ResNet [17]. These architectures are evaluated using both initialized parameters from scratch and transfer learning, which involves fine-tuning on ImageNet images.

The following are the key contributions of this research:

1. Deep learning adaptation to radiomics: This study investigates the application of deep learning to radiomics, specifically the non-invasive prediction of brain tumor grades using multi-channel MR images.
2. Prediction of brain tumor grade without manual segmentation or feature extraction: One notable accomplishment of this research is the prediction of brain tumor grade without the necessity for manual tumor volume segmentation or feature extraction and selection.
3. Transfer learning framework: The paper presents a unique framework for leveraging transfer learning to apply current pre-trained deep ConvNet models on multi-channel MRI data. This system has the potential to be extended to various MRI-based tasks.

The following portions of this work are organized as follows. Section II contains information about the data, such as how it was prepared in patch, slice, and volumetric modes, as well as some introductory information regarding ConvNets and transfer learning. The ConvNet designs developed in this work are introduced in Section

III. Section IV summarizes the experimental results, demonstrating their usefulness through qualitative and quantitative comparisons to existing relevant methodologies. Section V finishes the paper by providing concluding thoughts and conclusions.

2. METHODOLOGY

This section provides a quick summary of data preparation at three different degrees of resolution. Following that, an introduction to convolutional neural networks and transfer learning is provided.

Dataset

1. All the experiments were performed using the BraTS 2017 dataset[24][25], which includes data from the Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA) and information from the BraTS challenges of 2012, 2013, 2014, and 2015. There were 75 cases of low-grade gliomas (LGG) and 210 cases of high-grade gliomas (HGG) in this sample. The MRI scan set for each patient comprised four MRI sequences (or channels) with 155 2D slices at a resolution of 240 x 240. These sequences included native (T1) and post-contrast enhanced T1-weighted (T1C), T2-weighted (T2), and T2 Fluid-Attenuated Inversion Recovery (FLAIR) volumes. The data had already undergone skull stripping, been interpolated to a resolution of 1 mm³, and been aligned to a uniform anatomical template.
2. Each voxel in the ground truth images is labeled as either zero for normal pixels or nonzero for tumor cell portions. Fig. 1 shows an example image with the two grades displayed.

Figure 1 MR pictures from the TCIA database in the two categories (HGG, LGG) [26].

The image makes it clear how difficult it is for humans to discriminate between different groups based only on outward appearances. Therefore, using the abstract features that a ConvNet's deep layers have learnt could help with a non-invasive differentiation of these classes. Furthermore, using large-scale public domain datasets is probably going to have a greater therapeutic impact than dedicated, controlled prospective picture acquisitions.

Despite the fact that the BraTS 2017 dataset includes MRI volumes, there is insufficient data (only 210 HGG and 75 LGG patients) to train a 3D ConvNet with many trainable parameters, making the proposal of a 3D ConvNet model for classification impractical. The dataset also has an unbalanced class distribution, with roughly 35% of the classes in HGG and 72% in LGG. The method consists of creating 2D ConvNet models based on MRI patches that cover the tumor location and individual slices in order to

overcome these difficulties. Next, a ConvNet model based on multi-planar slices is developed to integrate volumetric data while minimizing the drawbacks of the unbalanced dataset. It is usually easier to determine the tumor grade from tumor patches than it is to classify the complete MRI slice. Here, the ConvNet concentrates on localizing inside the limits of the tumor in the image, enabling it to focus only on significant details and disregard irrelevant ones. But this method might overlook important local and spatial information that affects grade prediction. Although 2D slices and patches-based classification often produces high accuracy, using volumetric data from the dataset can improve the ConvNet's performance by offering a more thorough comprehension of the tumor's properties.

Following this methodology, we suggest how to build a multi-planar volumetric dataset using the BraTS 2017 dataset. Using a similar technology as previously described, 2D MRI slices are produced in this process in three anatomical planes: axial (X-Z axis), coronal (Y-X axes), and sagittal (Y-Z axes).

Proposed model

Convolution filter weights enable Convolutional Neural Nets (ConvNets) to independently learn abstractions at three different levels—low, middle, and high—from the input training data. Backpropagation is used during training to modify these weights. The data in the network is convolved with several filters, which act as detectors for edge, corner, and line features in connected portions of an image. These filters, which are layered, may automatically recognize similar patterns while ignoring unimportant regions. ConvNets are more trainable with fewer weights than densely linked layers thanks to two important principles: parameter sharing and connection sparsity. This reduces the possibility of overfitting and makes it easier to identify qualities that translate well. Several key ideas will be further examined in the context of ConvNets.

The input layer, convolutional layer, activation layer, pooling layer, and fully-connected layer make up a ConvNet's core layers. The batch-normalization layer and the dropout layer are examples of supplemental layers.

1. **Input Layer:** The input layer acts as the ConvNet's starting point, receiving the raw pixel values from the input image. In this case, the input is a 4-channel brain MRI patch or slice, represented as $I \in R^{4 \times w \times h}$ where w and h indicate the image's resolution.
2. **Convolution Layer:** The core component of a ConvNet is the convolution layer. A group of convolutional filters, also known as kernels, with the same height and width are contained within each convolution layer. For each convolutional layer, the number and size of these filters are user-specified. Each filter bank's input volume's depth (or channels) matches the depth of its filters. This layer performs the convolution operation between each filter and the input after receiving an image or feature map as input. In this procedure, the filter is slid—also called "strided"—across the image to produce a set of activation maps or feature maps equal in number to the filters that were applied. Using formulas unique to the convolutional operation employed, the output

feature map dimension from a convolutional layer is determined in multiple steps depending on the input dimensions, filter size, stride, and padding.

$$w_{out}/h_{out} = \frac{(w_{in}/h_{in} - F + 2P)}{stride} + 1 \quad (1)$$

where w_{out} and h_{out} are the width and height of the output, w_{in} and h_{in} are width and height of input image and P is the padding.

3. **Activation Layer:** The output responses from the convolutional and fully connected layers are subjected to a non-linear activation function, such as the rectified linear unit (ReLU), by the activation layer. ReLU is a preferred activation function in deep neural networks, valued for its computational efficiency and capacity to reduce the likelihood of vanishing gradients. It is denoted by $f(a) = \max(0, a)$.
4. **Pooling Layer:** After every convolutional layer, the pooling layer often reduces computing complexity by downsampling the complex response maps. It combines close together and maybe recurring features in the feature maps, making the representation smaller and more resilient to small changes in the image, such small details. Max pooling makes it easier to find the maximum feature response in small areas while ignoring exact locations, which improves translation invariance.
5. **Fully Connected Layer:** The features acquired from a sequence of convolutional and pooling layers eventually flow into a fully-connected layer, often a Multilayer Perceptron. The term "fully-connected" signifies that each neuron within a layer links to every neuron in the subsequent layer. This fully-connected layer aims to leverage these features to classify the input image into distinct classes, drawing from the information gleaned during training from the dataset.
6. Other components, like Batch-Normalization[27], aim to reduce the initial covariate shift. During training, Dropout [28], a regularizer, randomly deactivates network nodes. This method inhibits the inclination of all nodes in the fully connected layers to co-adapt with each other while forcing them to obtain a more sophisticated representation of the data.

Transfer Learning

First layers of a ConvNet often learn basic, low-level image properties that are useful for a variety of visual applications. The later layers, on the other hand, focus on advanced characteristics better suited to particular applications. For transfer learning, therefore, small tweaks to the latter levels are usually sufficient. Often, the final fully-connected layer of the pre-trained ConvNet is replaced with a new fully-connected layer that contains neurons that correspond to the classes in the new application. In essence, the pre-trained network uses the features of the previous layer to train a linear classifier with the remaining weights in its layers staying intact. However, more thorough fine-tuning can be required in situations when there is a significant difference between the source and target applications. Training a shallow neural network with one or more hidden layers is required for this. An effective method [21] is to begin fine-tuning

from the top layer and work your way down to deeper layers until you achieve the performance you want.

Architecture

Using the provided dataset as a basis for our work, we train a novel ConvNet architecture multi-Volume Net. This network will next be fine-tuned and subjected to transfer learning. The architecture of ConvNet is shown in Fig. 2. Using the multi-planar 3D MRI data, the multi-Volume Net is trained on the multi-planar volumetric dataset and uses its 3D representation to predict the tumor grade.

Fine Tuning

Using pre-trained architectures—VGGNet (16 layers) and ResNet (101 levels)—that were initially trained on the ImageNet dataset was a key component of transfer learning. Because ResNet uses global average pooling rather than fully-connected layers, it has a deeper model than VGGNet, but it is much smaller overall. To convert non-medical images to medical images, each model's final convolutional block and corresponding top-level classifier layers (fully-connected layers) have to be adjusted. Retraining the models on a new dataset with small to no weight alterations was the process of fine-tuning. In our instance, we carried out this fine-tuning in four consecutive steps:

1. Build the model's convolutional basis and input its weights.
2. Add a new fully-connected layer with a single neuron triggered by sigmoid in place of the last fully-connected layer of the pre-trained ConvNet.
3. Freeze every layer of the model, including the final convolutional block.
4. Next, we used the SGD optimizer with a very low learning rate to retrain the fully-connected layers and the final convolutional block.

3. EXPERIMENTAL CONFIGURATION

TensorFlow and Keras in Python were used to build the proposed ConvNet. A desktop workstation with an Intel i7 CPU (clocked at 3.40GHz) with four cores, 32GB of RAM, and an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 GPU with eight gigabytes of VRAM was used for the research.

Performance Evaluation

Because of the small sample size (285 patients) and unequal distribution of patients by class (210 HGG and 75 LGG patients), we suggest using a leave-one-patient-out (LOPO) test strategy for quantitative evaluation. With this technique, each iteration uses one patient for testing and the remaining patients for ConvNets training. This procedure is repeated for every single patient. Although LOPO testing is more computationally expensive, it provides a larger training dataset that is essential for ConvNets training. By giving unique test findings for every patient, LOPO testing proves to be reliable and pertinent in our application. When a patient is incorrectly classified by a classifier, this method allows for independent investigation. The proposed model is trained on the dataset using SDG with learning rate = 0.001 and momentum = 0.9. The batch size used is 32 samples.

20% of the training set is set aside as the validation set throughout the training phase. This subset is used to verify the ConvNet model at the end of each epoch, making parameter selection and overfitting detection easier. The following pair of metrics is used to assess the proposed model's performance in training and validation:

$$AC = (TN + TP) / (TN + TP + FN + FP) \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

$$F1 \text{ score} = 2 \times (\text{Recall} \times \text{Precision}) / (\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}) \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

Where *TN* represents true negative, *TP* indicates true positive, *FP* is false positive and *FN* represents false negative.

The training and validation accuracy, loss, and F1-score on the validation dataset for a single trial of the proposed ConvNets multi- Volume Net that are recommended are shown in Fig. 3. It was trained from scratch using the BraTS2017 dataset, coupled with information for the refined versions of two pre-trained ConvNets (VGGNet and ResNet101). The plots show how multi-Volume Net trains to get improved classification performance. It achieves maximum accuracy on both the training set (100%) and validation set (98%), in just 20 epochs. VGGNet and ResNet101, the two pre-trained models, perform similarly, with both models achieving about 85% accuracy on the validation set. After training, the model was assessed on the holdout test set using a majority vote procedure. In order to do this, test patients' individual patches or slices from the test dataset have to be categorized as HGG or LGG. By choosing the class with the highest number of categorized slices or patches, the tumor grade was ascertained. In the event that each class received an equal number of votes, the patient was classified as ambiguous. Multi- Volume Net achieved the maximum accuracy (97.19%) and no ambiguity, as shown by the results shown in Table I. And the time required to train each network for 100 epochs is displayed in the table II as the average of several runs.

Table III compares the suggested ConvNets with other shallow learning models that have been used in the literature for the same purpose in the past. These models require more work in manually segmenting the ROI/VOI and extracting features. Nine standard classifiers are listed in Reference [17] with their corresponding accuracy: i) Logistic Regression (LR), ii) Naive Bayes (NB), iii) Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Classifier (ANFC), iv) Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), v) Support Vector Machine (SVM), vi) Classification and Regression Tree (CART), and vii) k-nearest neighbors (k-NN). The BraTS 2015 dataset, which is a subset of the BraTS 2017 dataset and includes 200 HGG and 54 LGG instances, is the subject of the stated accuracy in [17]. 56 manually extracted three-dimensional quantitative MRI characteristics were used for categorization in this investigation, having been taken from the MRI of each patient. On the other hand, our method uses deep convolutional neural networks' learning power to automatically extract features from the data.

Table 1 LOPO test performed on three networks

SN.	Networks	Classified	Misclassified	Ambiguous	Accuracy
1.	VGGNet	239	40	6	83.86%
2.	ResNet101	242	42	1	84.91%
3.	Multi-Volume Net	277	8	0	97.19%

Table 2 Time taken for training

S.No.	Network	Training type	Time taken
1.	VGGNet	Fine-tuning	9.56 ± 0.02 min
2.	ResNet101	Fine-tuning	13.14 ± 0.03 min
3.	Multi-Volume Net	From scratch	134.48 ± 0.05 min

Table 3 Classification accuracy achieved by different deep learning models

Classifier	Accuracy	Description
VGGNet	83.86%	Tested and evaluated on MRI slices of 200 × 200 after trained on ImageNet dataset
ResNet	84.91%	Tested and evaluated on MRI slices of 200 × 200 after trained on ImageNet dataset
Multi-Vol. Net	97.19%	Tested and evaluated on multi planar MRI slices of 200 × 200 size
ANFC-LH	85.83%	Trained using 10 fuzzy rules and manually derived quantitative MRI features.
NB	69.48%	Trained using quantitative MRI features that were manually retrieved.
MLP	78.57%	Trained with a single hidden layer include 23 neurons and manually generated quantitative MRI features, with a learning rate of 0.1 and a momentum of 0.8.
SVM	64.94%	Trained using quantitative MRI features that were manually retrieved, using LibSVM with an RBF kernel and particular settings (cost = 1, gamma = 0).
k-NN	73.81%	The accuracy for k values of 3, 5, and 7 was averaged across scores after the subject was trained on manually extracted quantitative MRI features.
CART	70.78%	Trained using minimal cost-complexity pruning on quantitative MRI features that were manually retrieved.
PatchNet	84.91%	Evaluated on 2D MRI patches
SliceNet	90.18%	Evaluated on MRI slices

We perform a visual examination of the intermediate layer outputs to gain further insight into the ConvNets. Convolution kernels are key components of a ConvNet's effectiveness since they function as feature extractors from unsupervised learning. We may identify the description of the learned kernels by looking at the outputs of a convolutional layer visually.

4. CONCLUSION

This research presents a novel ConvNet design for non-invasive brain tumor grading that use MR tumor images to discriminate between HGG and LGG. It also investigates transfer learning by optimizing two ConvNet models that already exist for the same task. When compared to shallow learning models, Deep ConvNets improved classification accuracy on the test dataset by about 12%. Convolutional layer kernels/filters autonomously learnt to recognize unique tumor features that closely resembled different tumor grading criteria, as seen by the visualization of intermediate layer outputs. Furthermore, it was found that pre-existing ConvNets that were trained on natural images functioned well enough on MRI datasets when their final convolutional layer was fine-tuned alone. We achieved the best testing accuracy of 97.19% in our studies by proposing a methodology that uses multi-planar MRI slices to combine volumetric tumor information. According to this study, deep ConvNets may be a good substitute for surgical biopsy in the treatment of brain cancers.

Figure 2 Proposed ResNet101 architecture

Figure 3 Performance evaluated using five different architectures

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